

Next FOOD

EDUCATING THE NEXT GENERATION
OF PROFESSIONALS IN THE AGRIFOOD SYSTEM

D6.1: Dissemination, exploitation and outreach plan

WP6 - Communication, dissemination and exploitation

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Table of Contents

Executive summary.....	6
1 Context.....	7
2 Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Strategy.....	8
2.1 Objectives.....	8
2.2 Target Audiences.....	9
2.3 Methodology.....	10
2.3.1 DOE Strategy Phases.....	11
2.3.2 Stakeholders management.....	13
2.4 Expected Results.....	15
3 Dissemination tools.....	15
3.1 Project visual identity.....	16
3.1.1 The logo.....	16
3.1.2 Typeface & typography.....	17
3.1.3 Colour Pallet.....	17
3.1.4 The EU Emblem & Declaration of funding.....	18
3.2 Dissemination templates.....	18
3.3 Project website & platform.....	20
3.4 QR Code.....	22
3.5 E-mail account and mailing lists.....	22
3.6 Social media.....	22
3.6.1 Facebook page.....	24
3.6.2 Instagram Account.....	24
3.6.3 Twitter account.....	24
3.6.4 LinkedIn group.....	25
3.6.5 Google+ page.....	25
3.7 Audio-visual material – YouTube channel.....	25
3.8 Newsletters.....	26
3.9 Factsheet.....	27
3.10 Press releases.....	27
3.11 Brochure, leaflet, and poster.....	28
3.12 Project communication kit.....	28
3.13 Other dissemination material.....	29
4 Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach Activities.....	29
4.1 Network of Interest.....	29

4.2	EIP – AGRI abstracts.....	29
4.3	Mass media communication	30
4.4	Press releases	31
4.5	Publications	31
4.6	Posts in non-project channels	32
4.7	Participation in targeted events	32
4.7.1	Scientific conferences	33
4.7.2	Other Events	33
4.8	Collaboration with similar projects/initiatives	33
4.9	Organisation of project events	33
4.9.1	Round table talks/Stakeholder involvement	34
4.9.2	Workshops and training activities	34
4.9.3	Conference.....	34
4.9.4	Networking Events	35
4.10	Informal person-to-person meetings	35
5	Internal dissemination	36
5.1	Document sharing	36
5.2	E-mail communication	36
6	Strengths and responsibilities of the project partners	36
7	Monitoring, Reporting & Evaluation	38
8	Dissemination impact indicators	41
9	Timeplan for the first year of the project	42
10	Basic Principles.....	43
10.1	Compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation.....	43
10.2	Sustainable communication principle	43
11	Conclusions.....	43
	ANNEX 1 – Brand Design Manual.....	44
	ANNEX 2 – Templates.....	45
	ANNEX 3 – Banners	47
	ANNEX 4 – Leaflet & Newsletter	48
	ANNEX 5 – Identified Media Outlets	49
	ANNEX 6 – Scientific Journals & Conferences	50
	ANNEX 7 – Targeted Events	51
	ANNEX 8 – Reporting Templates.....	52
	ANNEX 9 – DEO Responsibilities Breakdown	53
	ANNEX 10 – Local Stakeholder Analysis.....	54
	ANNEX 11 – Communication Checklists.....	55

Table of Figures

Figure 1: CDE strategy phases	13
Figure 2: Stakeholder management grid	14
Figure 3: The NextFOOD logo in CMYK, Greyscale and, Black & White Versions ...	17
Figure 4: Typeface and typography for the NextFOOD project visual identity	17
Figure 5: The colour palette for the NEXTFOOD project visual identity	18
Figure 6: Indicative layout of NextFOOD funding declaration.....	18
Figure 7: NextFOOD deliverables' template	19
Figure 8: NextFOOD presentations' template	20
Figure 9: Indicative QR code for NextFOOD's webpage	22
Figure 10: NextFOOD's Project Facebook community page	24

Executive summary

The purpose of the following Deliverable is to detail the Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach (DEO) strategy and present the particular tools and activities that will be employed throughout the duration of the project, for this purpose.

NextFOOD as a project relies heavily on the proper communication and engagement of the community of the agrifood and forestry sectors, as well as the respective educational field. The following document provides the blueprint for the activities in a international/project and local level.

In particular, the document presents the context of the NextFOOD project (Chapter 1) and identifies the specific objectives of the communication strategy, the target audiences, the methodology for maximizing DEO and the expected results from the activities (Chapter 2). Moreover, it identifies the dissemination tools and describes how they are integrated into a whole to enhance the recognition of the project identity (Chapter 4). Additionally, it presents the DEO activities (Chapter 5) and particularises the procedures for monitoring the DEO impact and the timeline for the first year of the project (Chapter 7-9). Lastly, the document presents the basic horizontal principles concerning DEO (Chapter 10).

This DEO plan will be revised on months 16 and 24 of the project.

1 Context

Global changes pose important challenges to our generation from an environmental, social, and economic scope. The scientific community consensus moved on from accepting the human-induced climate change to the irreversibility of its effects. These effects are expected to pose great threats to the agrifood and forestry systems such as extreme weather events and shifting climatic zones. At the same time, the global population continues to grow and is expected to reach 9.7 billion in 2050. This growth goes hand in hand with a rise in demand for food, energy and other goods which originate from agricultural and forestry production. Thereby, the cultivation of renewable raw materials as suppliers of renewable raw materials for various technical applications is crucial. In order to meet these new challenges, the use of high-tech in fields and barns, new methods of plant production, computer use and other innovations needs to be implemented into the work of the farmers in the future.

The transition towards more sustainable agriculture, forestry, food and bio-based value chains, equipped to face the challenges ahead, requires a renewal and strengthening of the technical and soft skills of all concerned along the value chain from researcher, farmer, industry, end-user and policymaker.

Co-creation of innovation and knowledge in agriculture, forestry and related bio-value chains is crucial to overcoming obstacles preventing efficient implementation of innovative techniques and methods in the agrifood and forestry sectors.

The inherent trans-disciplinary nature of sustainable development thus poses new challenges to farmers, educators, and all agrifood system stakeholders. It is therefore critical to design educational systems that prepare budding current or upcoming professionals with competencies to push the green shift in our rapidly changing society.

Thus, the overall aim of NEXTFood is to generate an innovative European science and education roadmap for sustainable agriculture along the value chain from research via fabrication into application.

To reach the overall aim of NEXTFood, several objectives need to be met, including to:

- Create an inventory of the skills and competencies needed for a transition to more sustainable agriculture, forestry and associated bio-value chains,
- Facilitate case studies to identify gaps and needs
- Test new relevant curricula and training methods,
- Identify policy instruments that support the transition towards action-, and practice-oriented learning methods,
- Peer-review tools for evaluating the quality of the practice-oriented research,
- Create a platform for knowledge sharing

Under this light, NEXTFood aspires to exemplify how practice-oriented research can be instrumental to achieve: better collaboration between university and society, more innovation in the agrifood and forestry systems sector, and a progressive agrifood community ready to tackle complex sustainability challenges of the 21st century.

2 Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Strategy

The NextFOOD project views dissemination, exploitation and outreach (DEO) activities as processes that transcend the community and actors within the project's fields. The NextFOOD's overall strategy intends to communicate the actions and disseminate the results of the project to a multitude of audiences and engage in a two-way exchange with the interested parties. Towards this end, the consortium is committed to a strategy that takes into account strengths and weakness that could enhance or hinder the efforts to develop the outreach. The project partners, even during the proposal preparation phase, have identified relevant target audiences and stakeholders, as well as appropriate channels to reach them. The above efforts are being extended and broken down to a more granular level in the current deliverable.

2.1 Objectives

A crucial element for the success of the NEXTFOOD project is the participation of the local stakeholders and professionals in the agrifood and forestry systems in its actions.

In this respect, the NEXTFOOD Communication and Dissemination strategy aims to:

- Inform the general public about the importance of the agrifood and forestry fields
- Inform the general public about the need for a transition towards a more sustainable agriculture, forestry, food and bio-based value chains
- Persuade educators, professionals, policy makers that a new education paradigm is needed for the above to be equipped to face the challenges ahead, including the renewal and strengthening of the technical and soft skills
- Promote action-based learning strategies and methods as a mean to make agrifood & forestry systems more sustainable
- Engage Farmers, Farmers organisations, Forestry associations, Agricultural Advisory Services, Agrifood business and educational institutions into the project actions, such as case studies, roundtable etc.
- Raise awareness of regional, national and international policy-makers and public bodies concerning action-based strategies and methods in agrifood & forestry systems
- Encourage an open dialogue between multiple actors from different disciplines representing different parts of the agrifood and forestry system in diverse geographical locations with different natural and social conditions.
- Maximize the participation of stakeholders and professionals in the developed platform by a targeted promotion of its usefulness and potential
- Develop networks for the exchange of methods, tools and strategies and the exploitation of the results of the programmes on the spheres of educations, agrifood and forestry, and public policy
- Raise awareness to the agrifood and forestry professionals concerning the potential of adaptive lifelong learning, training, creativity and innovation
- Communicate with projects that have similar scopes and aspirations

Additionally, this deliverable aims to;

- Support partners in understanding and applying communication rules
- Improve the visibility of the project
- Ensure good quality project communication materials
- Ensure that the support from the EU has been clearly identified in all material
- Ensure efficient branding on a project and local level
- Support partners in managing communication to ensure that the above mentioned objectives are met
- Facilitate inter-partner exchanges

2.2 Target Audiences

NextFOOD has identified a number of potential target audiences to be reached in order to increase the impact of the project. The identified audience, in particular, are the following:

- Students and trainees in the Agrifood and Forestry fields & Farmers and forestry professionals: The project identified the particular audiences as important in the overall process as they will be integrated into the project actions. Moreover the above groups are the primary beneficiaries of the project. Attention will be given to relatively younger members of this group that are expected to be more open to innovation.
- Nextfood seeks to affect a paradigm shift in European universities, away from the usual linear, top-down, teaching approach and towards a cyclical, participative, action oriented system of learning, and therefore educators of the future professionals in the agrifood system is a key stakeholder group.
- Local, regional and national authorities: the interest of this group is linked with the important challenges authorities are facing with regards to global changes. Authorities should increase the capacity to address issues like the transition to a low carbon economy and to a more sustainable adaptive agriculture.
- Local, regional and national stakeholders involved in the decision making procedures in the Agrifood and Forestry fields as well as the respective education field. The above may include Farmers organisations, forestry organizations, producers associations but also agrifood businesses, agricultural advisory services and institutions undertaking both vocational and higher education.
- The scientific and education communities: the interest of these communities stems from the expected results of the project, which will allow them to assess their performance and/or adapt the curricula and research to face the new challenges.
- Project partners: Project partners are the first-hand multipliers of the project outcomes and results. The in-depth knowledge and understanding of all project aspects are crucial for the engagement of all the other target audiences.
- The general public: The general public is a secondary beneficiary of the current project. Nevertheless, the transition to a sustainable agrifood and forestry sector affects extensively the quality of life in all social, economic and environmental aspects.

The following table summarizes the main target groups, the reason why they should be reached, as well as the tools utilized towards this end.

Who	Why	How
-Students and trainees in the Agrifood and Forestry fields -Farmers and forestry professionals	-To directly engage them in the project -To inform them about the potential benefits from their participation in project activities -To integrate their perspectives (action-based research)	Brochures Participation in case studies Platform Website Workshops EIP-AGRI abstracts Newsletter
-Local, regional and national authorities -Local, regional and national stakeholders (e.g. Farmers organisations, Agricultural Advisory Services, Forestry Associations, Agrifood business etc.)	- To integrate their perspectives (e.g. inventory skills) - To inform them about the potential benefits from their participation in project activities - To engage them in project activities	Participation in case studies Platform Roundtable Workshops Newsletters EIP-AGRI abstracts
Teaching practitioners	- To support them in the adaption of a cyclical and action-oriented learning approach by providing with teaching tips, learning models and best practices -To integrate their perspectives (action-based research)	Knowledge platform Roundtable Workshops Newsletters EIP-AGRI abstracts
-Scientific community -Education	-To inform them about the potential benefits from their participation in project activities -To achieve better visibility of the project activities	Conferences On line communities Platform Roundtable Scientific Publications Website Workshops
- General public	-To inform them about the potential benefits from their participation in project activities - To achieve better visibility of the project activities	Brochures Press releases Social Media Videos Website

2.3 Methodology

To ensure the maximum possible DOE the NextFOOD project followed a specific methodology. The methodology has been employed in order to ensure complementarity among the different levels of the project and a common approach across all the geographical areas of interests. Nevertheless, special care was given to ensure that each case and distinct area will have the necessary space for specialization.

Towards this end, a step-wise approach was adopted, aiming to identify, stimulate interest, and engage involved parties. In particular, the methodology tackles the issue

of differentiated requirements and characteristics in each area with its respective stakeholders, objectives and areas.

The analysis is being coordinated by the WP6 with the support and contribution of all partners who provide information and insights through semi-structured questionnaires.

2.3.1 DOE Strategy Phases

The NextFOOD's DEO strategy is based on a successive step approach, it consists from four (4) different phases focusing on the development of an interest network, activation of participants in the project actions, iterative assessment and elaboration of the produced knowledge and finally dissemination and exploitation. The steps are presented in more detail below.

1st Phase: Identification and Development of Interest Network

The 1st phase of the methodology has to do with the identification and commitment of experts and stakeholders in the field. The aim of the specific phase is to develop a network interest that can function as a multiplier for the DEO of the project and take part in the later steps of the DEO strategy. A number of stakeholders signed a letter of support at the stage of submitting the proposal and they will be a part of this network.

In this phase each partner should take the necessary steps to ensure the commitment of at least five (5) individuals with knowledge on the specific fields of the project. Recruitment should be conducted via direct communication and utilization of the partners' expertise and knowledge concerning the field and the key actors in the area. These key individuals may come from educational institutes, professional organizations, local or regional governments, specialized agencies etc.

Once the network is identified, partners are encouraged to organize a focus group in order to facilitate a common understanding across the network of interest and how each individual can contribute as a multiplier of communication and impact. To this effect, partners should communicate the objectives, actions, expected results, as well as the DOE strategy of the project to the network of interest in order to achieve complementarity and synergy between the actors.

Objective	Commitment of at least 5 individuals for every pilot area (experts + project partners' representatives) to provide expertise and spread knowledge
Milestones	Organisation of the local Networks of Interest

2nd Phase: Action Motivation

During the second phase, the identified targeted audiences will be engaged to participate in the project's activities; namely the project case studies and trainings and the project platform. Preliminary stages in this phase may include the participation of partners' representatives in local events to communicate the scope and actions of the project and recruit participants. Special interest will be given to ensure gender representation since the analysis of experiences and viewpoints of both men and women is crucial for the project. Moreover, this preliminary stage will provide interested parties with the appropriate tools and motivation to participate actively in the activities of the project.

Possible target audiences for the case studies has already been identified by the leaders of the case studies and include undergraduate and postgraduate university students, researches, teachers, professors, farmers, food business representatives and entrepreneurs, forest professionals, extension specialists.

Interested parties will consequently engage in the project activities, either in specific case studies or in trainings concerning the use and benefits of the platform. Across all actions of the project a participatory, action-oriented approach will be utilized.

The particular phase is linked to the next phase of the DOE strategy i.e. the knowledge elaboration. More specifically these phases are part of an iterative process in that lies in the core of the project's rationale.

Objective	Participation in local case-studies - 5 Experts - 10 representatives from the local field community Participation in platform trainings, presentations Use of Platform
Milestones	Organization of Case Studies Organization of Trainings, presentations

3rd Phase: Knowledge Elaboration

The third phase of the DEO strategy concerns the engagement of members of the Interest Network of Phase 1 and the Action Community of Phase 2 in a series of local and international workshops and roundtables that elaborate on the knowledge produced in the previous stage, provide feedback and produce results. The above actions will take place on a case-study-specific setting, but also on an international/project level during the partner meeting and during a number of national roundtable talks or workshops. Indicatively, in the first cases workshops will focus on capturing local education governance perspectives and the international level on strategies for policy improvement. As mentioned above, this phase is interlinked with the Action Motivation phase in an iterative virtuous cycle. This process will yield specific results such as a policy brief, best practices cases etc. that will feed in the fourth stage of dissemination and exploitation.

Objective	Organization of workshops and roundtables - 5 Experts - 10 representatives from the local field community 10 representatives from the local field community
Milestones	Completion of workshops & roundtables

4th Phase: Dissemination & Exploitation

The fourth phase focuses on the dissemination and exploitation of the experience that was gathered though the previous three phases of the DEO strategies. All the participants of the previous phases will be represented in the 4th phase activities to communicate the relevance of the project, the objectives, actions and results on the specific context of the area. Moreover, the networks, action-learning and elaboration communities of the previous phases will produce the content and experience for i. partners and the WP6-leader to maximize DEO of the project. ii. Stakeholders to more

meaningfully engage in decision making, iii. agrifood and forestry professionals to strengthen their capacity.

Outputs of the 4th phase will be typical DEO results including:

- Project website
- Social Media posts
- Newsletters
- Presentations
- Informational material
- Presentations
- Audio-visual material
- Practice abstracts

These activities will take place throughout *the whole duration* of the project, gaining special feedback.

The following figure illustrates the above-motoned relationships:

Figure 1: DOE strategy phases

2.3.2 Stakeholders management

NextFOOD is a project that relies heavily on the participation of the local agrofood and forestry community. For all of the above phases, the engagement of stakeholders is of crucial importance for the implementation and the DOE of the project. Towards this end, and taking into account that the success of DOE activities relies on the use of the proper tools for the proper stakeholders, NextFOOD will engage in mapping the local stakeholders.

The commitment of resources to stakeholders that are within the community of the project partners may lead to limited outreach, while over-commitment of resources to a stakeholder that might be very active on the field, but with only limited capacity will likewise not induce the necessary momentum for the project.

Not all partners have the same influence on the decision process on a specific field. Some institutions are more influential than others. This can be either due to the structure of the process e.g. only some stakeholders have access to it or the specific characteristic of the stakeholder e.g. it is recognized as the most knowledgeable in the field.

Similarly, interest of stakeholders may differ. Influential stakeholders are not always interested and vice versa. Organizations with the legal mandate and responsibility might assess a specific issue as of secondary importance, while very interested stakeholders might not be eligible to participate in the decision-making process.

Taking the above into account, NextFOOD with the support of the partners will evaluate the influence and interest of the local stakeholders in each area.

This two-axis approach is graphically represented in a matrix as indicated below:

Figure 2: Stakeholder management grid

The classification of the stakeholders in the different quadrants provides insights concerning the proper message and management for each stakeholder and target audience.

- High-influence, High-Interest groups: These are the most important groups/stakeholders. Special efforts should be made that the specific groups actively participate and that representatives are engaged throughout the duration of the project.
- High-Influence, Low-interest: The specific group should be kept satisfied since it can hinder the efforts of the project. Moreover, whenever possible partners

should try to enhance the interest of this group to increase its engagement on the issue.

- Low-influence, High-interest: Stakeholders in this group though interested have low capacity to either hinder or promote the objectives and results of the project. Nevertheless, it is useful to keep this group informed as they would be very interested to move to the High-High quadrant.
- Low-influence, Low-interest: Stakeholders in this quadrant are of minimum importance and resources should be allocated respectively. Partners should simply monitor such stakeholders and groups, mainly to ensure that they have not moved to other quadrants.

The above analysis of stakeholders will be conducted for each partner enabling them to engage in proper activities. The results will be accessible in ANNEX 10 where a profile for each partner/geographical area of interested will be presented.

2.4 Expected Results

The expected results of the NextFOOD dissemination and communication strategy are the following:

- Increased capacity among stakeholder groups to go from knowledge about sustainability to responsible action in order to create a more sustainable agrifood system.
- Increased public awareness concerning the agrofood and forestry systems and their importance to alleviate vulnerability to global changes
- Increased target group knowledge about the project's results such as professionals' skills needed for transition, curricula assessment tool, methods for knowledge co-creation etc.
- Increased target group knowledge about the tools for professionals in the fields of the project, as well as the repositories where these tools can be found
- Dissemination, promotion, and exploitation of the programme results such as the education road-map for sustainable agriculture, the best agricultural practices etc.
- Increased public awareness concerning good practices that promote among others climate change adaptation, supply chain innovation etc. in the project fields
- Increased awareness among stakeholder groups about the benefits of engaging in an action-oriented cyclical learning approach compared to the traditional linear way of learning.

3 Dissemination tools

The following section presents the dissemination tools that will be employed throughout the NEXTFOOD project in order to reach out to the identified target audiences. These tools will be utilized in accordance with specifications of the current deliverable.

3.1 Project visual identity

The Project Visual Identity is based on an overall approach of interconnected elements that have as a scope the development of a narrative concerning the project. Thus even though the logo is the cornerstone of the visual identity it is supported by other visual elements that construe a comprehensive visual strategy. Taking into account the above the visual identity includes the following

Concept and Values: The concepts and values are the core of the visual identity bringing together the different elements in a single narrative. The concept and values are expressed in a graphic way through the logo, colour pallet etc.

Colour palette: The pallet consists of an organized series of colours that are linked with the concept and values of the project's brand and are represented in the logo, typography, icons and templates of the project.

Typeface & typography: They consist form a series of fonts that in conjunction with the colour pallet are manifested in the project's templates.

Logo: The logo is the graphic emblem and symbol that has as a main scope to communicate the concept and values. It is closely tied with the utilized colour pallet and font type. The logo will have different versions depending on the context that it is used.

- **Primary logo:** the main logo utilized in the main communication and dissemination activities
- **Secondary logo:** used in specific contexts in many cases together with the primary one

Templates: Templates are the manifestation of the visual identity in ready to use material for several media formats of physical or electronic nature (e.g. presentations, documents, social media, letters etc.)

The EU Emblem & Declaration of funding: Part of the projects identity and narrative is its support from the EU. The project will highlight EU funding in all material while at the same time making sure that the produced material will clearly state that they reflect only the author's view and that the EU Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contain. In this regard, all material will be produced taking into account all the provisions of the Grant Agreement.

The Visual Identity is designed to present the project internally and externally by

- providing visibility and "recognisability"
- developing a symbol for external entities
- promoting a public image and reputation
- highlighting the relationship and structure between the constituting members of the project, including the EU
- providing a comprehensive communication medium
- developing a specific narrative, for the recognition, dissemination, communication of the project and engagement with the project.

3.1.1 The logo

The logo is the cornerstone of the project's graphic identity and is key for a successful visual communication and brand recognition of the project. In order to achieve the maximum possible recognition the logo will be used in all the dissemination materials and documents produced and related to the project.

The logo consists of the project acronym incorporating visual elements that reference to the basic attributes of the project, namely agriculture and food. The logo is presented below (Figure 1) in CMYK, Greyscale and Black & White.

A detailed guide for the use of the logo has been developed and disseminated to partners to ensure its proper use in conjunction with other visual elements ANNEX 1.

Figure 3: The NextFOOD logo in CMYK, Greyscale and, Black & White Versions

3.1.2 Typeface & typography

For full application of the NextFOOD brand design, the following type specifications for print publications and stationery are recommended. The sizes and heights are optimised for use with the grid described in the manual of ANNEX 1

Title Font: Arial 24pt Colour: 83/71/65 RGB

Subtitle Font: Arial 12pt

1. Headline 1 Font Arial 20pt Colour: 83/71/65 RGB

2.1 Subtitle Font Arial 16pt Colour 177/210/91 RGB

3.2.1 Subtitle Font Arial 12pt Colour 198/156/109 RGB

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, ex est tale aliquando conclusionemque. Saepe complectitur at eum.

Nusquam tistique denique ad nec, affert graeci cum ea, magna laudem mel te

Quotes/remark/emphasis

Footnote, Italic, 6/8

Figure 4: Typeface and typography for the NextFOOD project visual identity

3.1.3 Colour Pallet

The NextFOOD Project had identified a specific colour pallet to represent the identity of the project. The specific pallet is to be used throughout the communication and dissemination material of the project to enhance the project's branding. The colours are presented below, along with their respective identification in Pantone, CMYK, RGB, and HEX.

Explanation:

Pantone:
Spot colours.

CMYK:
Process-color printing, 100 color gradations per channel
C = cyan, M = magenta, Y = yellow, K = black

RGB:
Colour sample for monitor display with 256 gradations per channel
R = red, G = green, B = blue

Hex:
System similar to RGB, however with gradations from "00" to "FF" (hexadecimal) per channel. This system is preferably employed for designing websites.

Color	Pantone	CMYK	RGB	HEX
	729 U	22/39/58/10	192/150/109	C0966D
	Neutral Black U	54/54/55/54	83/71/65	534741
	7554 U	45/47/53/38	115/99/87	736357
	374 U	39/0/76/0	177/210/91	B1D25B

Figure 5: The colour palette for the NEXTFOOD project visual identity

3.1.4 The EU Emblem & Declaration of funding

In addition to the above in all produced documents and dissemination material in addition to the NEXTFOOD logo, the EU details will be included. In particular, the EU emblem as well as a clear declaration that the project received funding from the EU and the Horizon 2020 Programme for Research and Innovation will be included in accordance with the respective Grant Agreement Articles (27.3, 28.2, 29.4, 38.1.2). The EU emblem will be accompanied with the text "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738". The above will be added in all printed and electronic material in a layout similar to the following:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

Figure 6: Indicative layout of NextFOOD funding declaration

Moreover, whenever the EU emblem is used together with another logo the EU will have appropriate prominence.

As mentioned above in any dissemination of results it will be clearly indicated that the material reflects only the author's view and not that of the European Commission Research Executive Agency. In particular, the following text will be included "The present deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains."

All of the above points are incorporated in the project templates presented in the ANNEXES 1-4

3.2 Dissemination templates

To ensure the common branding across all partners and mediums, a series of templates have been developed by the WP6 leader. All developed templates follow

the distinct visual identity of the project to enhance identification and recognition. The templates will be shared with all partners through the proper communication channels.

Deliverable template

All deliverables of the project will follow a specific recognizable visual identity promoting the project's brand. The template that has been developed in MS world to be readily available by all partners adopts a specific style.

The template consists of a title page that incorporates the title of the project along with its logo in a prominent position. The centre of the page features the title of the deliverable, while the lower part of the page is dedicated to informing the reader about the source of the project's funding. More specifically, the lower part includes the EU emblem and a clear statement of the funding source, along with the proper disclaimer in accordance with the provisions of the Grant Agreement. The second page features a table summarizing the document's information and history, along with the authors and contributors of the specific deliverable. The above pages are common along all deliverables and are followed by a section that includes the table of contents and the table of figures. All pages with the exception of the first one include a footer that contains the projects logo and the EU emblem.

Figure 7: NextFOOD deliverables' template

Presentation template

The WP6 leader has developed a presentation template to be used as a dissemination tool for all partners. The specific template will be utilized by all partners and in all activities including internal and external presentations and especially in national and international scientific conferences. The template incorporates the EU emblem, funding declaration and disclaimer according to the provisions of the Grant Agreement.

Figure 8: NextFOOD presentations' template

3.3 Project website & platform

The NextFOOD project will develop a website and a platform to serve as the main communication, dissemination and exploitation tool. In this respect, the website and the platform will be organized in such a way that will serve the specific characteristics of both the general public and the targeted audiences of the project. Additionally, the website will incorporate a platform with free subscription access where the results of the project including teaching tips and learning materials will be presented especially for teaching practitioners in the field of agriculture and food and other targeted audience. A limited access part of the webpage will host project internal material, such as minutes etc. The WP6 leader will acquire a domain like the following in order to develop the project's website:

www.nextfood.eu

www.nextfoodproject.eu

www.nextfoodH2020.eu

In particular the website will incorporate the following elements.

NextFOOD overview

- General Objectives and Methodology
- Information about the NextFOOD platform
- Information about partners
- Presentation of case studies and areas of interest
- Social media links
- Information about project events

Public Outcomes

- Deliverables
- Presentation
- Factsheet
- Manuscripts
- Newsfeed

Platform (Specialized section)

- Case study reports
- Models
- Teaching tips
- Lessons-learned
- MSc Theses
- Best Practices Abstracts
- Event subscription
- Project calendar

In addition to the above the website will be developed according to the following principles:

- Ease of use
- Clear identification of the project's mission statement
- "3 click principle"
- Responsiveness to different kind of devices
- "Open source" website content management system
- Audience analysis through Google analytics
- Archiving of old information in the content management system

The website will be continuously updated, throughout the duration of the project. The WP6 will be adding content as case studies advance and deliverables are concluded. Moreover, the website will be kept after the finalization of the project for a period to be determined at a later stage. The free access subscription of the platform will make it possible to build on the knowledge gathered in Nextfood in other projects and future initiatives. After the completion of this period, the project's website will be archived on to a movable drive or in other permanent storage.

The website will be developed in British English and in accordance with the provisions, requirements, and/or obligations of the Grant agreement, EU guidelines, gender issues, and stakeholder groups. All partners will add a link to their organization's websites and/or other websites that are directly linked to the project (e.g. University Laboratory websites). Moreover, partners will promote the project in other online communication and dissemination platforms they manage such as social media, blogs, fora etc. The WP6 leader and the partners will additionally encourage engaged stakeholders to further promote the project through their own web-based platforms, especially during the periods of case studies.

Finally, the WP6 leader will follow the audience of the website through platform subscription and Google analytics. In particular, the WP6 will analyze traffic to identify the audience groups and their needs in order to improve the layout and content of the website and make it more attractive and efficient as a dissemination tool.

3.4 QR Code

A QR code will be created to direct mobile users to the NextFOOD webpage, from where they can access additional information about the project, its events and apply for them on line. The code will be incorporated in the dissemination material and specifically to their printed versions to multiply the potential for DEO. A indicative QR code for NextFOOD's webpage is presented below.

Figure 9: Indicative QR code for NextFOOD's webpage

3.5 E-mail account and mailing lists

In addition to the website presented above, the project will have a public general-purpose e-mail address e.g. info@nextfood.eu. The e-mail address will be presented in dissemination material including the website, leaflet, social media accounts etc. and will serve as the main input source for enquires concerning the project. The account will be managed by the coordinator of the project who will forward any queries addressed specifically to partners of the project to them. For practical reasons, all other partners will continue using e-mail accounts they already utilize.

For the facilitation of communication, a series of mailing lists will be created. For all mailing lists, either for internal or external communication, the WP6 leader will take measures to ensure that the GDPR provisions will be respected. The use and storage of personal data in WP6 will comply with the ethics guidelines elaborated in the Nextfood deliverables D8.1 Human and D8.2 Data storage. There will be two mailing lists according to the level of engagement and/or interest of the parties concerning the project. The 1st mailing list will serve internal communication procedures and will include all those directly involved in the implementation of NextFOOD. A 2nd mailing list will also include associate partners, stakeholders, experts, potential platform users etc. As a first step, all partners will be asked to identify possible interested parties and encourage them to subscribe/consent into receiving news from the project. The mailing list will be also enriched during the implementation period through subscription using the website tool and participation in physical project events. This second mailing list will be used to communicate invitations to project events, the project's newsletter, leaflet and brochure dissemination, project updates etc. and serve as a tool for the continuing communication and engagement of the community.

Mailing lists will be managed from the project leader and according to the provisions of the GDPR and the Data Management Guidelines of the Data Management Plan.

3.6 Social media

NextFOOD will utilize the major potential that social media have in reaching out and engaging audiences both of the general public and the specific project stakeholders.

NextFOOD has already created a Facebook page and will create a Twitter account, an Instagram account, a LinkedIn group, a Google+ page, and a YouTube channel. All of the above will be linked to the project's website and platform and presented in dissemination material to make sure that all channels are communicated to the maximum possible audience. All partners will be encouraged to upload project-related information and material to support communication and dissemination of the project both international and locally in their respective area of interest. The WP6 leader will be moderating all social media outlets to ensure that proper use and/or attribution will be safeguarded.

The NextFOOD's aim is to engage the maximum audience from several demographic groups. Taking into account that different social media target and/or are utilized by different audiences NextFOOD utilizes all of the above mentioned social media. Moreover, the project will take into account the nature of the message to be conveyed and adapt it respectively to the social media and the audience to enhance communication and dissemination.

The project identifies a preferred audience, based on the expected characteristics for beneficiaries from the results. The characteristic of this audience are presented bellow :

- Area: case study sites
- Age: 25-35
- Gender: All
- Interests:
 - Topic: Profession, Hobbies and activities
 - Keywords: Agroecology, Sustainability development, Green Agriculture, Environmentalism, Education etc.

For all social media accounts, the WP6 leader with the contribution of the partners will share accounts to maximise attendance and popularity. Particularly, the accounts will be specifically promoted to:

Accounts and/or groups of

- Local, regional and national authorities and public organisations, mainly from the case studies sites
- Local, regional and national stakeholders involved in the decision-making procedures for agrifood systems, forestry, education etc.
- NGOs and associations active in the above-mentioned fields
- Farmers' organizations and/or professional associations especially in the pilot areas
- Similar EU funded projects
- Partners' social media accounts
- Other social media account the project partners manage

Partners that will be engaged in case studies are especially encouraged to utilize all available dissemination channels to which they have access, such as local authorities, universities, media etc. accounts, to raise awareness about the actions implemented in the area. To minimize the lag phase between the event and the social media posts partners will be encouraged to post in their respective communication channels, including the project identifications (e.g. hashtag) and the WP6 leader will retain the

right to re-post, endorse or alter the post to ensure compliance with the Grant Agreement provisions.

All NextFOOD Social Media pages and/or accounts will utilize British English as an official language. Nevertheless, partners and especially those that will host a case study are encouraged to use other languages such as the native one used in the area.

Each partner will be responsible to post and/or provide content for at least one social media post per month.

3.6.1 Facebook page

A NextFOOD Facebook page has already been developed under the name “NextFOOD” and the address @nextfoodinnovativescienceandeducation. The administration of the Facebook page will be under the WP6 leader, whose role will be to manage all features of the page. This includes messages uploading, posts publication, confirmation of posts and comments as well as role assignment for community members. In addition to the WP6 leader, the project leader will have editing privileges on the page to ensure second-level supervision of the page and content. In this respect, the project leader will have the same privileges as the administration with the exception of assigning roles to community members. On a need-to-be basis, more editors may be added during the implementation period of the project.

Figure 10: NextFOOD's Project Facebook community page

3.6.2 Instagram Account

The NextFOOD Instagram account will be utilized to reach out to younger audiences and will be based primarily in visual communication tools. Partners facilitating case studies will be encouraged to upload photos, short videos, and or gifs to celebrate the diversity of geographical areas, cultures, practices etc. that the project engages with. The recommended Instagram identifiers for NextFOOD project are:

NextFOOD_H2020

Hashtag: # NextFOOD_H2020

3.6.3 Twitter account

The NextFOOD twitter page will be used as a main electronic channel to spread the project news and announcements concerning the actions, outcomes, results of the project. The account will be utilized to communicate and disseminate (audio)-visual material, links for public deliverables, though its main focus would be to disseminate activities while they take place. The recommended twitter identifiers for the NextFOOD project are:

Twitter account: @NextFOOD_H2020

Hashtag: # NextFOOD_H2020

In addition to the above hashtag, the #HorizonEU will be utilized in important news and announcements of the project. Furthermore, partners will be encouraged to use their own tweeter accounts to follow, retweet or tweet actions about the project using the above-mentioned hashtag.

3.6.4 LinkedIn group

The WP6 leader will create a LinkedIn group in order to reach out to an audience that has a more business and/or professional profile. LinkedIn as a social media focuses on professional networking and is often used as a specialized communication and dissemination medium. The NextFOOD LinkedIn will aim to develop a network of professionals, experts, organizations, policymakers and entrepreneurs that can be primary or secondary stakeholders.

All stakeholders identified and engaged in local actions will be encouraged to become part of the NextFOOD LinkedIn project in order to develop a network of actors that are more interested in specialized information such as about the results and outcomes of the case studies, scientific publications etc. All members of the LinkedIn groups will be managed and approved by the WP6 leader who is the group administrator. The WP6 leader will also have the responsibility for the account's editorial control, which can be overruled by the project leader and the managing committee.

The proposed name for the NextFOOD LinkedIn group is "NextFOOD_H2020"

3.6.5 Google+ page

The NextFOOD Google+ page will be an informational page linked with the respective YouTube account. The aim of the page would be mainly to clarify and present all the necessary information concerning the project as it will be 'uploader' of the videos. The page will also be useful in case of other Google tools being adopted during the implementation period of the project. The Google+ page will be visually incorporated in accordance with the visual identity of the project and will provide a link to the project's website.

3.7 Audio-visual material – YouTube channel

Audio-visual material can be of great importance when it comes to promoting the NextFOOD project. Short videos such as animated features and/or documentation videos from the project actions are often more attractive and informative for the general public than brochures. Taking the above into account the NextFOOD project will utilize YouTube as the main audio-visual dissemination medium harvesting at the same time

the potential that Tweeter, Instagram and Facebook give to promote the content to larger audiences.

The audio-visual material will include:

- Short promotional video about the project that would be hosted in the main video on the YouTube page
- Short promotional video about the project platform
- Micro videos presenting each one of the case studies.
- Micro videos about the project activities, events, meeting, presentations etc.

All partners will be encouraged to promote the YouTube Channel through their respective audio-visual outlets and/or social media accounts and pages.

As with all other Social Media, the upload will be managed and moderated by the WP6 leader under the supervision of the project leader and Project committee. In the case of audio-visual material in the native language of a partner and/or material where English is not easily discernible, the respective partner should provide the necessary subtitles in English.

The WP6 leader will not be responsible for audio-visual uploads of partners in other social media, including GIF etc. though will have the right to remove content that is not in accordance with the Grant Agreement Provisions concerning Dissemination Material and/or content that might be considered outside of the project's strategy and scope.

It is recommended that the WP6 leader will be responsible to produce the promotional videos about the project and the project's platform, and also the micro videos about the project meetings. Partners will be responsible to develop a micro – video for the case studies and/or participation in other events.

3.8 Newsletters

NextFOOD will utilize newsletters to inform relevant audiences about the progress of the project. More specifically, newsletters will be used to present key developments to interested audiences and keep stakeholders engaged. Newsletters will be circulated every six months by the WP6 leader and their content will be contributed by all project partners. They will be primarily circulated in electronic form through mailing lists and will be uploaded in the respective social media accounts and the webpage. Printed copies may also be distributed, though only if partners consider it necessary and in a specific audience of primary stakeholders.

While the compilation of the newsletter will be the responsibility of the WP6 leader, the content will be based on the reports that partners will provide concerning their respective activities, developments on the platform, presentations, workshops, roundtables, meetings, publications etc. Partners will be contacted regularly by the WP6 leader to provide their contributions.

The newsletter will have a specific layout presented in the ANNEX 4. The template follows the overall visual identity of the project and clearly provided information about the funding, as well as the disclaimer.

The newsletter will be addressing the following issues:

- Short presentation of the project
- Announcements concerning the progress of the project
- News from case studies and WPs
- Details about conferences, meetings, events, roundtables or publications.

NextFOOD partners will be encouraged to identify possible newsletter recipients and disseminate the newsletter to their contacts interested in the project. Additionally, there will be a specific provision that would allow interested parties to subscribe to the newsletter¹.

The WP6 leader will be responsible to develop and disseminate a newsletter every six months. All partners will be responsible to engage in activities to develop a mailing list in the first 12 months, and provide material to be incorporated in the newsletter at least 1 month earlier before the newsletter release. Partners' input will be submitted through the reporting templates in ANNEX 8.

3.9 Factsheet

The factsheet will be a document that will comprehensively compile the main project information; namely its outline, goals, key issues, approach, expected outcomes and results, the project consortium etc. It will be utilized as communication material during the projects' events and case studies and will be available on the project website.

The WP6 will be responsible to develop an informational factsheet every year. Partners will be responsible to provide the data one month in advance of its dissemination.

3.10 Press releases

Press releases will be the main communication medium to mass media, with regards to the project activities. Press releases will be scheduled so as to coincide with important events or project milestones and will include information either concerning a future event or results achieved in by the project. Their main focus will be the local, regional and national media outlets (press, TV, radio). Therefore, their wording and focus will be accordingly adapted avoiding any use of specialized terms and/or jargon to ensure accessibility to the general public. Moreover, they will focus on the local/regional/national benefits of the project.

The WP6 leader will be responsible for issuing press releases on an international level, while on a local level this will be the partners' responsibility. All partners should follow the above-mentioned guidelines and get approval from the WP6 prior to the press release announcement. Lastly, WP6 will be responsible to hold partners accountable when they do not issue press releases according to the DEO plan.

Each partner is recommended to disseminate 2 – 3 press releases every year.

¹ As stated in Chapter 9 of the Deliverable all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities will take into account the GDPR provisions and ensure compliance with them.

3.11 Brochure, leaflet, and poster

The scope of the projects' brochure is to promote the platform and serve as a communication material for the case studies. A double-sided A4 brochure template has already developed by the WP6 leader, though the specific content has not yet been finalized. The brochure is recommended to contain a general overview of the NextFOOD project and incorporate a section focusing especially on the case studies. In particular, the leaflet is recommended to include at least the scope, expected results, and methodology of the project.

Partners involved in case studies will be encouraged to translate the leaflet in their native language and disseminate the material to maximize the communication of project actions. The leaflet will be circulated by electronic means but it will be also available in physical copies for project conferences and other public events.

In addition to the above, a poster will be created and used in all project conferences, partner meetings, roundtables etc. The poster will provide limited information about the project and its main scope will be to draw attention and drive the public into actively reaching out to the website, platform and the other mediums of project communication and dissemination. The poster will be utilized in synergy with the leaflet in public events.

In all of the above material the logo, title and specific keywords of the project will be included, along with the EU emblem and funding declaration. Additionally, links to the project website and social media accounts will be provided in such a way so as to encourage the audience to visit them. Lastly, all of the above material will follow the visual identity of the project brand and use visual elements to attract attention.

The brochure and leaflet of the project are presented in ANNEX 4.

The WP6 leader will be responsible to develop the brochure, leaflets and poster in English and provide the templates to all partners. Partners will be responsible to adapt them in the native language if deemed important and disseminate in a local level.

3.12 Project communication kit

The WP6 Leader will prepare a project communication kit for each partner. The kit will include i. the leaflet in English language, ii. a poster, and iii. an overview presentation. The above kit will be communicated to all partners, along with all the other templates to ensure that a common visual identity will be used across the board. The overview presentation will also include basic key points with regards to the identity of the project.

Partners will be responsible to translate with the most possible accuracy the leaflet, poster, and or presentation in their native language. Moreover, all partners will be strongly advised to use the above-mentioned communication kit in any actions, events etc. of the projects, including the scientific conferences in which they will take part.

The overview presentation will be updated every six months to ensure that all the important developments of the project are included and presented. Special attention will be given to including all the produced results of the project.

The communication kit will be developed in English by the WP6 while all partners will be responsible to adapt it in their native language.

3.13 Other dissemination material

The NextFOOD project may produce physical material to ensure a more long-lasting presence of the brand. Such material may include, USB sticks/cards, pencils, bags, t-shirts or other material that will prominently include the NextFOOD logo. In addition to the above, all material will also clearly bear the EU emblem. Partners involved in case studies will commit themselves to disseminate this material to support stakeholder, professionals and public engagement. The above-mentioned material will be strategically disseminated in events to increase NextFOOD's visibility primarily to the project target groups and only secondarily to the project partners, in order to maximize the outreach.

4 Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach Activities

4.1 Network of Interest

The development and management of the network of interest will be an activity that will take place throughout the duration of the project. Its main scope is to work as a multiplier for the DOE activities of the project, while at the same time function as a participants' broker. The process for its development is presented in more detail in the previous section since it constitutes the first phase of the overall DOE strategy. The management of the Network on a local level will be conducted by the respective partner in the area, while the overall international project-level network will include representatives of the local level.

Efforts will focus on identifying and engaging representatives from European and national level, agrifood and forestry professionals and entrepreneurs, experts in these fields, universities and research centres, as well as participants in the decision and policy-making on the field.

4.2 EIP – AGRI abstracts

According to the EIP-AGRI:

“Through the website's interactive functions, users can share innovative project ideas and practices, information about research and innovation projects, including projects' results, by filling in the available easy-to-use e-forms. Various EIP-AGRI-related publications are available for download on the website, providing visitors with information on a wide range of interesting topics.”

NextFOOD will utilize EIP-AGRI to increase DEO of the expected results.

In particular, the resulting innovative knowledge and easy accessible end-user material from this project will feed into the EIP-AGRI website for broad dissemination. The end-user material to be produced contains a substantial number of summaries for practitioners in the EIP common format ("practice abstracts"), including the characteristics of the project (e.g. contact details of partners, etc). A full package of practice abstracts is needed for the project, containing all the outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice. A "practice abstract" is a short summary of around 1000-1500 characters which describes a main information/recommendation/practice that can serve the end-users in their daily practice. The set of practice abstracts will be submitted as a deliverable in the project and in the 'EIP common format' to EIP. The guidance to be followed for these practice abstracts and some explanatory text and examples from ongoing projects are available on the EIP-AGRI web site ([http:// ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/content/eip-agri-common-format](http://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/content/eip-agri-common-format)). More specifically it is expected that 100 EIP-AGRI abstracts will be submitted by the finalization of the project organized in two different batches. In particular, the activity action is linked with the D6.7:Practice abstracts part 1 – before the first review meeting [M18] and D6.8 : Practice abstracts part 2 – before the second review [M36].

The WP6 leader will be responsible to adapt the abstracts in the EIP-AGRI format. Partners involved in the particular task will have to provide content to the WP6 leader 3 months prior to the deliverable deadline. Each case leader delivers at least one per year and each WP leader deliver at least two per year

4.3 Mass media communication

Mass media communication will be the main informational medium with which the project aims to reach out to the general public. The project will engage in DEO activities with conventional and web-based mass media outlets like TV channels, radio, newspapers, and magazines. All communication activities utilizing mass media outlets will be specifically compiled and phrased to be accessible to the largest possible audience.

Activities that will take specifically into account mass media communication include the following

- press releases
- audiovisual material
- factsheets & infographics
- overview presentations

The WP6 leader will develop general guidelines and talking points as an indicative interview walkthrough for the partners.

All partners are encouraged to engage in mass media communication in a local, regional and national level on a regular basis. Mass media communication activities on an international level will be managed by the WP6 leader and through the official email account of the project.

All partners will document and provide information to the WP6 leader about mass media communication activities following the specialized template and provide the

respective video, sound-file, clipping of the communication activity. All partners will be contacted to identify possible mass media outlets such TV channels, news agencies etc. for the mass media communication campaign. An indicative list of relevant mass media is presented in ANNEX 5.

4.4 Press releases

Press releases will be prepared on an international level by the WP6 leader, while partners will be responsible for press releases on a local level.

International Press Releases will be prepared in English, though partners will be encouraged to translate and circulate them in their national, regional and/or local level. The project's target is to circulate at least 15 press releases during the implementation period, on a European, national, regional and local mass media outlets (TV, Press, radio both conventional and web-based). All press releases on any level will be uploaded and archived on the website, in order to be readily accessible. In addition to the mass media outlets identified by the project partners presented in ANNEX 5, the NextFOOD project may engage the following outlets to maximize communication.

[EPI-AGRI](#) Newsletter

[Panorama magazine](#) of the European Commission

[EC Research & Innovation](#): The website is a major communication source for EU-funded research results to the media and the general public.

[Community Research and Development Information Service](#): CORDIS offers the ability to download press releases of EU-funded research.

[AlphaGalileo](#): AlphaGalileo is another outlet that the project may utilize to communicate results. AlphaGalileo is an important source concerning European research news. The leader of WP6 will take all the necessary steps in order to have the right to post press releases, events etc.

Other channels: Other channels that will be explored are the [European Environment Agency](#) and the Community, [Health, Agriculture and Food Executive Agency](#).

4.5 Publications

The NextFOOD project will produce a number of articles to be published in specialized press (printed or online) and scientific, peer-reviewed journals. The overall target for publications is 15 with at least two (2) scientific peer-reviewed publications and one academic monograph that will serve as a lasting record of the research supporting long-term impact through education, further research, and wider policy development.

The WP6 leader will encourage all partners to contribute and actively participate in the development of the publications.

Non-scientific publications

The NextFOOD project's target is to publish at least twelve (12) articles will in specialized press media. The specialized press media would indicatively focus on agriculture, agroecology, forestry, food processing, education, and environment. All partners will be contacted to identify possible specialized press media in a European, national, regional and local level. An indicative list of relevant specialized press media is presented in ANNEX 5.

Partners managing a case study will be responsible to produce one non-scientific publication every two years.

Scientific Publications

The NextFOOD project aims in publishing at least two (2) scientific papers in Journals that provide Open Access to all their content in accordance with the requirement of the Grant Agreement. The targeted fields will be those of Agrofood systems, Agriculture Education & Training, Agroecology, Forestry, Nature systems biology and application. All partners will be contacted to identify possible journals for the publication of the scientific articles. An indicative list of relevant Journals is presented in ANNEX 6. Only journals with a high impact factor relatively to other journals in the same field should be considered for publication.

The WP6 leader will support writing and submission of scientific publications. The authors' team will be proposed and finalized by the Steering Committee.

4.6 Posts in non-project channels

A number of non-project channels will be utilized to promote the communication and dissemination of the project, such as blogs, LinkedIn, Facebook etc.

The WP6 leader will communicate the NextFOOD actions in several LinkedIn groups relevant to the project's scope and interest such as Agrofood systems, Agriculture Education & Training, Agroecology, Forestry etc. Indicatively, the following groups may be reached:

- Agricultural Education
- Sustainable Agriculture Education Association (SAEA)
- AGROFOOD Experts
- "H2020 BIOTECH" BioEconomy, Agriculture, Forestry, Food, BioScience & BioTechnology
- World Institute for Action Learning (WIAL) Network

Partners will be responsible to upload one post in a non-project channel every year.

4.7 Participation in targeted events

A fruitful way to enhance communication and engagement to the project from identified and potential stakeholders is to participate in relevant events. All partners will be encouraged to participate in such events to enhance dissemination of the project results, but also stakeholder participation and outreach to professionals and students

in the relevant fields. During these events, partners will circulate dissemination material (e.g. brochures, leaflets etc.) to participants.

The participating partners will document and communicate relevant reports and photos through dissemination tools such as social media. To minimize the lag phase between the event and the social media posts partners will be encouraged to post in their respective communication channels, including the project identifications (e.g. hashtag) and the WP6 leader will retain the right to re-post, endorse or alter the post to ensure compliance with the Grant Agreement provisions.

All partners will be asked to provide specific information about the events in which they participated through a communication template particularly developed for this purpose presented in ANNEX 8.

4.7.1 Scientific conferences

Scientific Conferences are very important events for the dissemination of new scientific knowledge and networking. The NextFOOD will participate in conferences that are relevant to the fields, scope and objective of the project. All partners will be contacted to identify possible conferences for participation. An indicative list of relevant conferences as they were identified by the project partners is presented in ANNEX 6.

Implicated will be responsible to participate to at least 1 event every year.

4.7.2 Other Events

The NextFOOD project will encourage partners to take part in local events in order to communicate the project actions and disseminate the project results. Such events may include festivals e.g. food festivals, professionals associations events, farmers and/or producers events etc. The abovementioned events can be very important in disseminating the results of the project to practitioners, enhance participation to the project platform, as well as expanding the network of interest.

All partners will be contacted to identify possible events in which the NextFOOD project could participate to engage professionals and stakeholders. An indicative list of relevant events is presented in ANNEX 7.

Partners will be responsible to participate to at least 1 event every year.

4.8 Collaboration with similar projects/initiatives

The NextFOOD programme will identify projects and initiatives that are active in similar fields for possible collaboration. The purpose of this activity is to strengthen the network of interest and enable potential synergies across the different projects. In particular, the WP6 leader will identify projects on the EU, national, and regional level on the agrofood and forestry sectors. WP6 will explore in cooperation with the partners on a local level the potential to exchange views and experiences, maximize the impact and increase the collective dissemination and exploitation.

4.9 Organisation of project events

A number of events will take place during the implementation period of the project. One important defining characteristic of this project is that it is interdisciplinary, cross-sectoral and cross-cultural. As such, it aims to impact the behaviour of a number of distinct audiences, including practitioners of the primary and secondary sectors, consultants and other service suppliers, researchers, students and policymakers. The creation of a common discourse among these disparate groups is among the chief objectives of the WP6, first at partner and then at external stakeholder level. Thus the abovementioned events will involve stakeholders, professionals, students and other interested parties.

WP6 will support all partners towards the organization of these events and will organize respective events in its geographic area of interest. In all of the events, special attention will be given to include and engage members of the Network of Interest.

The following events will take place:

- Roundtables/stakeholder meetings
- Workshops
- Training Activities/User meetings
- Conference
- Networking Events

4.9.1 Round table talks/Stakeholder involvement

All partners in the consortium and all participants in the stakeholder platform will participate in roundtable talks. These roundtable talks are intended to allow experts from the different stakeholder groups an exchange of specific knowledge and dialogue on critical questions on a high academic level but also on a public non-academic level.

Two (2) roundtable talks will be organized at each one of the annual consortium meetings as well as in parallel to the collaboration activities in the different work packages.

4.9.2 Workshops and training activities

All partners in the consortium and all participants in the stakeholder platform will participate in workshops and training activities. Improving the communication and understanding between researchers and practitioners will facilitate the research transfer and accelerate the innovation processes aimed at competitive and sustainable farming.

There will be 4 workshops, one in each consortium meeting that will be organized by the respective partner organizing the meeting. The WP6 leader will support the respective partners for the organization, should partners require it.

All partners will organize at least one training/user meeting during the project's duration. As with the workshops, partners will be responsible to organize the trainings/user meetings, while WP6 will support partners, should any need arise.

4.9.3 Conference

The project leader will be responsible to organize a final conference in Brussels. The conference will take place during the final months of the project and will include a Policy Brief session to relevant authorities and decision makers.

4.9.4 Networking Events

There will be at least two networking events during the duration of the project. In these events, a presentation of progress in case studies and preliminary conclusions will be presented to external stakeholders. Moreover, interactions between all interested parties will be encouraged to serve as useful feedback for the key partners in terms of successful implementation of the project. The above-described networking events, will be held, one in the Czech Republic and one in Italy, at the end of the second and third years of the project respectively.

The following table summarizes the project events, including, type, time, number and involved partner.

Event	When	How many	Involved partner
Roundtables	2 per annual meeting	4	SLU USB AFS MUC
	Together with different WP and case activities	3	WP and case leaders
Workshops	1 per partner meeting	4	SLU USB AFS MUC
	Together with different WP and case activities	3	WP and case leaders
Training activities/user meetings	1 per partner	19	All partners
Conference	Final meeting	1	SLU
Networking Events	In conjunction with the partner's meeting	2	USB UNIBO

4.10 Informal person-to-person meetings

All partners will be encouraged to engage in person-to-person meetings with key multipliers to enhance the dissemination, exploitation, and outreach of the project. The meetings will aim towards informing key persons concerning the benefits of the project so that the information will be conveyed to their respective audience. Furthermore, they will intend on increasing the exploitability of the project's results.

All partners will be contacted to identify possible multipliers and encouraged to attempt a person-to-person meeting with them. Such key people may be policymakers, heads of professional organizations, CEOs of influential agrifood and/or forestry businesses, people with in-depth knowledge of the decision processes, heads of educational organizations etc. The meetings will be conducted throughout the project duration. Partners conducting such meetings will document them and report them to all project partners.

5 Internal dissemination

In the following section, the internal communication pathways are presented in order to ensure that throughout the duration of the project the collaboration between partners will be unhindered. More specifically that:

- all partners have access to the same information at the same time
- all project developments are readily available and accessible by all partners
- no informational bottlenecks hinder flow between partners
- common communication procedures are followed
- there is no excess informational burden to partners

5.1 Document sharing

The project utilizes OneDrive as a means to ensure that all documents are shared and accessible by all partners, at all times. Moreover, with the development and launch of the website and platform, finalized versions of deliverables will be uploaded on the public domain. The finalized versions of internal documents will be also uploaded to the platform of the website with limited access only by the project partners.

5.2 E-mail communication

Mailing lists will be utilized for communication among the project partners. To that end, the WP6 will re-establish the interest of the all partners to be part of the mailing list and inform them about their right to opt out of the list in accordance with the GDPR provisions. Taking the above into account a mailing list that will allow the communication with all involved parties and partners will be created. The mailing list will be managed by the coordinator who will ensure its proper use and that all relevant emails will have the identification “NextFOOD” prior to the topic. Moreover, the coordinator will encourage partners to conduct all communication through one channel and in a way that all relevant partners are informed at once.

6 Strengths and responsibilities of the project partners

In the following section the strengths of the project partners concerning the fields of the project are presented. These strengths were utilized to develop a plan concerning the engagement of the partners in the different tasks of the DEO plan. The strengths of each partner are described below.

Partner	Expertise	Farm network management	Action learning approaches	Agroecology	Sustainable agriculture	Social sciences	Forestry	Entrepreneurship	Policy development	Food studies	Gastronomy	Programme Management	Farmers' Training	Value Chain Development	Content Development	International Collaboration
SLU		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
LU																
UNIOR			X		X	X	X			X	X		X		X	
USB		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X
NMBU			X	X	X	X				X		X				X
AFS		X	X	X		X			X				X	X		X
UNIBO			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X		X	X
Bioinstitut		X	X	X	X								X	X	X	X
Skogforsk			X					X	X	X				X	X	
ACRCM		X				X								X		
CIHEAM		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
WHH		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	
SDF		X	X	X		X	X		X	X	X				X	X
Mekelle		X	X	X	X	X	X						X	X		
ATEITH			X	X		X	X		X	X						
ISEKI			X					X	X	X		X	X		X	X
MUC		X	X			X		X	X	X	X			X	X	X
UNISG			X				X				X	X	X			X
UChile		X	X	X	X					X		X	X		X	X

In particular, the breakdown of partners' responsibilities concerning WP6 is presented in the following table, while responsibilities of partners concerning the specific DEO activities are presented in ANNEX 9.

Task	Sub-Task	Leader	Partner
Task 6.1 : DEO plan	Development of the dissemination, exploitation and outreach plan	AFS	
Task 6.2 : Public dialogue	Project Webpage	AFS	Bioinstitut, ACRCM, ISEKI
	On-line platform	AFS	Bioinstitut, ACRCM, ISEKI
	Dissemination material	AFS	Bioinstitut, ACRCM, WHH, SDF, Mekelle, ISEKI, UChile
Task 6.3: Events	Round table talks/Stakeholder involvement	AFS	All partners
	Workshops and training activities	AFS	All partners

7 Monitoring, Reporting & Evaluation

The project has developed a scheme for the monitoring and reporting of the DEO activities. The scheme is based on the formal time plan concerning the deliverables of WP6 which is the following:

Deliverable	Month
D6.1:Dissemination, exploitation and outreach plan	2
D6.2:Data management plan	6
D6.3:Webpage online	6
D6.4:Information material for scientists and public no.1	18
D6.7:Practice abstracts part 1 – before the first review meeting	18
D6.6:Report on the dissemination and training activities no. 1	24
D6.5:Information material for scientists and public no. 2	36
D6.8:Practice abstracts part 2 – before the second review	36
D6.9:Practice abstracts final part	48
D6.10:Minimum of two publications in international peer-reviewed journals	48
D6.11:NextFOOD Monograph	48
D6.12:Report on the dissemination and training activities no. 2	48

In addition to the above the DEO plan will be updated approved by the steering committee in months 16 & 24.

For all dissemination, communication and exploitation activities the WP6 leader will be responsible and all partners will report to the WP6 leader. The WP6 will report to the project coordinator, who will be responsible to resolve any conflicts, should they occur. Partners will be responsible for their local dissemination activities such as local press releases, articles etc. To this end, partners will be responsible to engage mass media and engage the stakeholder communities in their area of interest. The WP6 will facilitate the process of providing a first evaluation of stakeholders, media outlets and events.

Coordination concerning the WP6 will be contacted between personnel from the WP6 leader and an assigned contact point from each of the other partners. For purposes of reporting the WP6 leader has developed a number of templates that the partners WP6 contact points should fill in and communicate with the WP6 leader. The templates regard publication and events and are presented in ANNEX 8. In addition to the above the WP6 contact point should attach clippings, videos, sound files, photos or other appropriate material for the documentation of the dissemination activities.

The WP6 leader will be responsible to monitor the dissemination activities, their impact and their compliance with the time plan and encourage partners to keep up with their respective goals. The indicators and time plan that are presented in the following sections will be employed as yardsticks for the overall performance of the project dissemination activities.

More specifically, WP6 leader will be responsible for:

- monitoring project communication activities:
 - answer requests related to communication in info@nextfood.eu
 - monitor the project website
 - make recommendations for social media use
 - track project social media accounts

- ensure that project managers have all the necessary material to ensure proper and correct visibility
- ensure partners track record of media coverage including response to press releases
- collect feedback from partners to assess CDE activities
- compile the reports concerning communication activities

Each partner will be responsible to

- follow visibility rules
- send the layout of major materials e.g. deliverables for approval before finalisation
- document events, collect all necessary data for communication
- document responses to press releases
- send reports on events according to the templates

A more detailed mapping of responsibilities can be found in Annex 9.

The following table summarizes the recommended partners' responsibilities per tool/action.

Tool/Action	What	Who	When/How Often
Visual Identity	Develop	WP6 leader	M3
Templates	Develop	WP6 leader	M3
Webpage & Platform	Provide Content	All partners	M5
	Develop/Upload	WP6 leader	M6
	Update every	WP6 leader	every 6 months
QR Code	Develop	WP6 leader	M6
E – mail account	Develop address	WP6 leader	M6
	Mailing list	All partners	M12
Social Media	Posts in Project's Accounts Endorse/retweet etc.	WP6 leader	1 post/month
	Posts in their account about the project Endorse/retweet etc.	All partners	1 post/month
Audio-visual	Promotional video for Project	WP6 leader	M18
	Promotional video for Platform	WP6 leader	M18
	Micro videos about meetings	WP6 leader	One month after the completion of a meeting
	Micro videos about case studies	Partners Managing a case study	One month after the completion of a case study phase
Newsletters	Compile	WP6 leader	1 every 6 months
	Manage mailing lists/send	Coordinator	1 every 6 months
	Provide content	All partners	1 month prior to dissemination
Factsheet	Compile Disseminate	WP6 leader	1 every year
	Provide content	All partners	1 month prior to dissemination
Press releases	Creates disseminates in international lever	WP6 leader	2 every year
	Create disseminates in national/regional/local lever	All partners	3 every year
Brochure, Leaflet, Poster	Develops template Disseminate	WP6 leader	M12
	Provide content	All partners	M9
	Adapt Disseminate	All partners	M18

Project Communication kit	Develop in English	WP6 leader	
	Adapt in Native Language		
Other Dissemination Material	Approve	WP6 leader	N/A
Network of Interest EIP-AGRI Abstracts	Develop Contacts	All partners	M12
	Adapt in format	WP6 leader	M18 (50) M36 (50)
	Provide content	All partners	M15 (3 each) M33 (3 each)
Publications Non-scientific	Support	WP6 leader	Throughout the project duration
	Publish	Partners managing a case study	One every two years
Publications Scientific Papers/Monograph	Support	WP6 leader	Throughout the project duration
	Write - Submit	Author' team approved by steering committee	M48
Posts in non-project channels	Publish	All partners	one every year
Participation in targeted events	Take part in Conference	SLU USB AFS UNIBO WHH SDF Mekelle ATEITH MUC UCH	one every year
	Take part in events	All partners	one every year
Collaboration with similar projects	Identify – Invite	WP6 leader	M12
Roundtable Stakeholder Events	Organize – Invite participants	SLU USB AFS MUC	According to meetings (7)
Workshops	Organize – Invite participants	SLU USB AFS MUC	According to meetings (7)
Training Activities	Organize – Invite participants	All participants	1 every two years (38)
Conference Networking Event	Organize – Invite participants	SLU	M48 (1)
	Organize – Invite participants	USB UNIBO	According to meetings (2)
Person – to – person meetings	Organize – Invite participants	All partners	M18

8 Dissemination impact indicators

For the evaluation of the DEO impact a number of indicators were developed. These indicators which represent the minimum expected outreach are presented below.

Measure	Indicator	Target Value	Source/methodology
NEXTFOOD Online platform	Number of Visitors to the platform	10,000	Statistics monitoring of the project website
Social networks	Number of followers	1,000	Monitoring NEXTFOOD profiles on such networks
Poster	Number of times poster presented	15	Partner network information, presented in the DEO reporting
Brochure	No of brochures distributed	2,500	Partner network information, presented in the DEO reporting
Written articles and Sc. Publications	No of Publications	15	PDF-copy of the article/paper published
Press Releases	Number of Press Releases	5	PDF-copy of the article/paper published
Policy Brief			Vocational training award authority Certified trainers, teaching practitioners
Stakeholder platform meetings	Number of average attendants per meeting	15	Attendance list of the event
Case Studies	Number learners involved in the cases	250	Attendance list of case sessions
Final High Level conference	Number of attendants	100	Attendance list of the event

9 Timeplan for the first year of the project

The timeplan for the DEO of the first 12 months is presented below. The time plan will provide guidance to partners and function as a monitoring tool for DEO activities.

Actions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Website - Finalize content - Upload - Create links				X	X	X						
Mailing lists - Create Internal - Create External	X						X					
Social media - Create LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, Google+, and YouTube groups/accounts - Invite members/friends/followers for NextFOOD social media groups/accounts		X	X									
Deliverables Data Management Plan				X	X	X						
Newsletter							X					
Brochure, leaflet, factsheet								X	X	X	X	X
Poster - Prepare and Print						X						
Publications/ Articles												
Press releases - Identification of European and national media with high visibility - Identification of important project milestones and events for which press releases should be prepared - Preparation of content and dissemination of press releases	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Audiovisual material - Content development										X	X	X
Participation in relevant events - Identification of international events, seminars and conferences and information of other partners - Identification of events, seminars and conferences at national level - Poster/ presentations in international events - Presentations in similar initiatives events	X											X
Project events - Case Studies						X						X
Collaboration with similar projects/ initiatives - Identification of similar projects/initiatives - Communication with similar projects/initiatives					X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

10 Basic Principles

10.1 Compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation

All communication, dissemination and exploitation activities will take into account the relevant provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation concerning the management and protection of data. More specifically, all the necessary measures will be taken to ensure that information such as e-mail addresses, telephone number, audio-visual recordings etc. will be managed in accordance with the above mentioned regulation throughout the period during which the project will be communicated through physical or electronic means.

10.2 Sustainable communication principle

NextFOOD supports the production of communication material that is strictly necessary for meeting its goals. Material such as bags, pens, notebooks, USB sticks will be utilized only for very specific communication activities is clearly explained and justified. A justification for the above will be presented to WP6 by the proposing partner and should include what the use of the material will be after the completion of the activity. Prior approval by the WP6 will be necessary for the production of such material.

11 Conclusions

The current DEO aims in detailing the strategy, actions and relationships needed to maximize the effects of the NextFOOD project on the agrifood and forestry sectors, and their respective educational field. As the project evolves, the DEO plan will be updated to incorporate the developments. In particular, the DEO plan will be revisited in months 16 and 24.

ANNEX 1 – Brand Design Manual

PDF file link

Press Release Template (Indicative)

Title Press Release

Day Month Year | Place (City, Country)

Press Release

Sub headline adding more information in 1-2 lines (optional)

Lead/introduction

Copy text ewitz on queju vinre, esni uz balomre in rindupu doan. Neukifa sina lenim dakai Olla gefeph rhuss nekosha kalain, hers dock in bulassa. Kisuaheli neumyx doclenim dakai herangu de sal. Henrie onunim herero wubu.

Subhead

A one-line headline inserted in the body of a story to break up the monotony of paragraphs. Kalain, hers dock in bulassa. Rewitz on gofello queju vinre, esni uz balomre in rindupu doan. Neukifa sina lenim dakai herangu de sal. Henrie onunim herero en schemkra Deck in no dol deck noviton. Olla gefeph rhuss nekoscha kalain, hers dock in bulassa.

Short paragraph about your programme (at the end)

NextFOOD's core mission is to identify, describe and disseminate effective approaches to food production and forestry. We use active, personal wording to engage the reader.

For further information please contact:

Address

City / Name and surname Job title

Country

t: +12 3 456 789 101

m: +12 3 456 789 102

f: +12 3 456 789 103

email@address.eu

Name of the projecy

t: +12 3 456 789 101

m: +12 3 456 789 102

f: +12 3 456 789 103

info@your-programme.net

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ANNEX 3 – Banners

Facebook Banner

Roll-Up Banner

ANNEX 4 – Leaflet & Newsletter

Leaflet Template

Newsletter

ANNEX 5 – Identified Media Outlets

TBD from questionnaire

ANNEX 6 – Scientific Journals & Conferences

TBD from questionnaire

ANNEX 7 – Targeted Events

TBD from questionnaire

ANNEX 8 – Reporting Templates

Publication Reporting Template

Field	Input
Date	DD/MM/YY
Task	Please fill in the task that the publication was disseminating
Description	Please describe the type of publication name of the medium title of article
Estimated Reach	Estimation of individuals reached
Target Audience	Please describe which target audience the publication is more probable to reach
Partners involved	Partner's name
Feedback	Please provide any feedback that you might have had
Link	Please provide a link to the publication
File	Please upload a file (photo, scan, sound file, video, pdf) of the publication.

Event Reporting Template

Field	Input
Event title	Please write down the title of the event
Type	Seminar/ infoday/ bilateral meeting/ fair trade/ stand
Place	City, Country
Dates	DD/MM/YY
Event aim & purpose	In 150 characters please identify the objective of the event
Relevance to the project	In 150 characters please identify what is the impact of the event to the project
Type of audience	Please describe the audience attending the event and connection with targeted audience
Estimated size of targeted audience	Please provide estimation in number
Geographical scope of event	Please clarify if local/regional/national/international
Partner(s) involved	Please write down the name(s) of the partner(s)
Goal of presence	Please explain why you attended the event
Feedback from the audience	Please provide any feedback that you might have had
Stakeholders engaged	Please provide a link to the publication

ANNEX 9 – DEO Responsibilities Breakdown

Action	WP6 Leader AFS	ALL Partners	Coordinator/Committee
Webpage	Develops/Updates	Provide content in a regular base	Holds WP6 Accountable Resolves Conflict
Social Media	Manager/Moderator	Upload Provide content in a regular base	
Audio-visual	Edits content Uploads content Circulates content	Create relevant material	
Newsletter	Compiles Circulates Develops and updates mailing list	Provide Content Disseminate	
Articles	Approves Creates Content Disseminates	Provide Content Disseminate	
Brochure, Leaflet, Poster	Develops template Disseminates	Adapt Disseminate	
Factsheet	Compiles Disseminates	Document Provide Content	
Press releases	Approves Creates Content Disseminates	Provide Content Create Content Disseminate Update and integrate the media list provide Performance data to the WP6	
Project Communication Kit	Develops template	Adapt Disseminate	
Other Informational Material	Create	Disseminate Translate content Develop using the available templates	
Publications	Compiles Edits Submits	Provide Content	
Participation in targeted events	Approves	Participate Document Provide Content	
Workshops & training activities	Approves	Participate Document Provide Content	
Abstracts	Compiles Edits Uploads	Document Provide Content	

ANNEX 10 – Local Stakeholder Analysis

TBD from Questionnaire

ANNEX 11 – Communication Checklists

Keep in mind while you write

Sentence length

- Keep sentences short. Ideally they should be between 15-20 words and never over 30.
- Very short sentences can be very effective
- Make one point per sentence

Vocabulary

- Use everyday words
- Avoid jargon and acronyms

Tone

- Be conversational and engaging
- Avoid slang and colloquialisms
- Use first and second personal pronouns for the project and the reader.
- Use active sentences.

Structure

- Put the most important fact in the beginning of the sentence
- Use bullet points

Content

- Make sure you provided answers to the 6Ws

Storytelling

Use the Inverted pyramid

- Put most important information on the top – least important to the bottom.

Use a lead paragraph

- Give reads the main points, summarize the whole article, insight interest
- Reply to the 6 W's: Journalists use the five "W's and the H": who, what, where, when, why and how.
- Keep in between 50-60 words

Make it interesting for the press

- Link the projects objectives and expected results with the actuality
- Showcase the relevance of the project with the audience of the media
- Present a story with which the audience can associate
- Keep journalist contact list and provide them with interesting stories
- Condense the most crucial details from a project in a sentence achieve promotion

Press Release Checklist

- Use a clear and short headline
- Identify your target audience
- You can start with a questions
- Avoid technicalities and jargon
- Use correct grammar
- Use catchy high resolution photos and/or graphics

On Social Media

- Feature short videos or graphics about the project
- Feature infoprographics
- Take advantage of key days e.g. earth day to showcase the relevance of the project
- Share catchy visuals from the project
- Share project news in other media links
- Share news from collaborating project
- Keep one consistent communication style (e.g. informative, personal, motivational)
- Use hashtags and links to provide additional information